

METHODS OF WORKING WITH AN EXPLANATORY DICTIONARY IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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Abstract. *The article discusses the main ways of interpreting a word in a dictionary, analyzes the methodological principles of working with an explanatory dictionary in elementary school.*

Keywords: *word, meaning of the word, interpretation of the meaning of the word, types of tasks on the explanatory dictionary, the game "Scrabble", dictation "Guess the word!", lexical dictation.*

To say that students graduating from school should write competently would be to prove the obvious. At the present stage of development of our society, this provision does not require argumentation. It is generally accepted that the school is obliged to equip its pupils with strong spelling skills.

The word is the most important unit of the language, the carrier of meanings. Words and their combinations denote specific objects and abstract concepts, while emotions are expressed in words. The richer the vocabulary of a person, the, consequently, he has a wider choice and a more accurate, more original and expressive design of thought.

Every teacher, of course, knows that working with a dictionary is an obligatory part of the work on developing the culture of speech of students in Russian lessons. The sources of quantitative and qualitative growth of the vocabulary of primary school students are exercises of textbooks of the Russian language, works of books for reading and, finally, the rich and expressive speech of the teacher himself.

It is difficult to overestimate the importance of dictionaries in the life of any person. As you know, reading dictionaries, regularly referring to them improves the culture of speech. Dictionaries expand the individual phraseological stock and vocabulary, introduce the norms of the Russian language, prevent the misuse of words, their grammatical forms, pronunciation.

Dictionaries enrich our knowledge of the language, deepen the interpretation of the word, help the development of logical thinking.

Now any publishing house offers a lot of dictionaries and reference books specifically for primary school children. The first dictionary should become for a primary school student not a list of vocabulary words that need to be remembered as a multiplication table, but a real book with the most important, most necessary, most interesting words of the Russian language. Communication with such a book will be the first experience of familiarization with reference literature, on which, in fact, the emergence of interest in the dictionary as a special kind of reference book depends, the formation of the ability to independently turn to the dictionary for the necessary information.

Now linguistic dictionaries of various types have been created for younger schoolchildren: spelling, orthoepic, explanatory, etymological, dictionaries of antonyms and synonyms. The choice of spelling dictionaries is especially rich. This is natural, because it is the spelling dictionary that is the most popular type of Russian language reference book by the school and family.

Entering school, modern children often already know how to read, their reading circle consists of works of children's literature. First-graders have no experience with the dictionary. That is why it is important for a primary school teacher already in elementary school not only to teach how to use a dictionary, but also to arouse interest in working with it, to make him feel joy, pleasure, satisfaction from working with this book. In such work, the methods of reading-communication and reading-viewing, developed by Professor N.N. Svetlovskaya, come to the aid.

In the first grade, when the future reader is still being formed, it is necessary to start work from the preparatory stage – reading-viewing.

The method of reading-viewing the book is also relevant for dictionaries of the Russian language, so the primary school teacher will not have difficulties in organizing acquaintance with the dictionary during the lesson. Getting to know the cover is reading the title: the author's last name and title. A page-by-page review of the book will help answer the questions: what does the dictionary teach us? Why is it needed? Why is the book called that? How is the dictionary similar to other books? How is it different? Familiarity with the dictionary begins at the same time as working with the alphabet. Children study vowels and consonant letters – they search for these letters in the dictionary: in the alphabet, among the highlighted letters in the text, at the beginning of the title words. After getting acquainted with the alphabet, the skill to highlight this sequence and use it when searching for the right word is honed.

Working with the alphabet according to the dictionary will allow the children to make small scientific discoveries. Already first graders can count the number of pages in the dictionary for a particular letter. Younger schoolchildren will see with their own eyes what, for example, the frequency of letters in the Russian language is. At the lessons of acquaintance with the dictionary by reading-examining, students will learn how the entire dictionary and its separate page are built, what is the "symbolism" of the dictionary (graphic highlights, abbreviations), the application is considered: lists of proper names, patronymics, names of cities, spelling rules. All this is a preparatory stage of working with the dictionary.

The main purpose of working with an intelligent dictionary in elementary school lessons is to enrich the vocabulary of children, teach them to find words in the dictionary, teach them to interpret the meaning of a word themselves, because, as you know, the vocabulary of children is quite small. They often understand the meaning of the word superficially, inaccurately, and sometimes they do not understand it at all.

The main work in the lesson can take place in two directions proposed by the author of the "Spelling Dictionary" P.A. Grushnikov. The first is the use of the dictionary as a special reference. The second is the use of the dictionary as a textbook of the Russian language. The teacher should understand the importance and necessity of working with dictionaries, organize systematic work with them in the classroom. Russian should be avoided in two typical situations involving dictionaries: the first – the teacher introduces the dictionary to the children and offers to refer to it independently in case of difficulties; the second typical situation is episodic work with dictionaries, when from time to time the teacher includes the dictionary in practical work in Russian lessons. It is necessary to exclude such work when the word "dictionary" means either a list of vocabulary words at the end of a textbook of the Russian language, or his own homemade dictionary (usually in a notebook), which begins with everyone's interest, and not all students in the class complete a twelve-page notebook. Children can fall in love with a dictionary only in the classroom where the teacher himself loves dictionaries. If there is not a single reference book in the classroom for the

teacher himself, if the teacher himself does not constantly turn to dictionaries for help and advice, one cannot expect his students to reach out to dictionaries. An educational dictionary, a dictionary for a junior schoolboy is a serious problem of modern methods of the Russian language. This problem has been dealt with and continues to be dealt with by our leading scientists: D.N. Ushakov, S.E. Kryuchkov, A.N. Tikhonov, P.A. Grushnikov, Z.A. Potikha, M.R. Lviv, etc.

Professor M.R. Lviv emphasizes that the purpose of publishing dictionaries for students is to provide them with reference literature on the language, thereby increasing the level of their independent work, providing them with high-quality, selected language material. Russian Russian should be a language material that will contribute to the development and formation of a culture of speech, material for reflection, observation, reflection on the mysterious and amazing Russian language. M.R. Lviv is the author of such school dictionaries as "School Dictionary of Russian language antonyms", "Dictionary of synonyms and antonyms of the Russian language", "Learning to distinguish words Russian Russian Dictionary and their meanings: Dictionary of polysemous words, thematic groups of words, homonyms, paronyms, synonyms, antonyms", "Dictionary of Antonyms of the Russian language", "Explanatory Dictionary of Antonyms of the Russian language" Russian Russian School Dictionary of antonyms contains widely used antonyms in the modern Russian language, combined in pairs.

Dictionary entries define the meanings of antonyms, provide information about antonymic synonyms, antonyms nests, as well as examples from works of fiction demonstrating the use of antonyms. The dictionary helps students to master the expressive means of the Russian language.

There are a number of provisions defining the organization of work with the dictionary of students:

Firstly, working with the dictionary has an educational and educational impact on the formation of the personality and worldview of schoolchildren. Thanks to working with dictionaries, students master a variety of skills that are necessary for practical activities in the future.

Secondly, students receive explanations of new words that are incomprehensible to them due to participation in vocabulary work. In addition to gaining knowledge about new words, students have the opportunity to analyze and clarify the meanings of already known words. The work done opens up new knowledge and understanding of the richness of the dictionary to students.

Thirdly, the most common way of analyzing the meanings of words is carried out by considering word usage in the modern language.

Fourth, vocabulary work with students should be a qualitatively organized and systematic work. Such work should be carried out during the study of all sections of the Russian language.

Didactic material helps teachers to develop a system of working with dictionaries. It should be noted that the importance of vocabulary work lies in the fact that human thinking proceeds to a greater extent in linguistic forms, which provides an opportunity to influence human behavior with the help of language. Therefore, it is important to take a responsible approach to the selection of language vocabulary, because in this way the teacher influences the thinking and emotions of students.

However, most often in explanatory dictionaries a full interpretation is given, therefore, first of all it is necessary to teach children to find the main word, then to name the main word

themselves and check the dictionary. Having taught you to understand where the main word is, you can proceed to acquaintance with secondary signs.

When starting to get acquainted with the dictionary, preparatory work should be done to repeat the alphabet: children should clearly imagine where this or that letter is in the alphabet: at the beginning of it, in the middle or at the end.

Tasks for the dictionary should be aimed at the meaning of the word, that is, it is necessary not only to teach them to find words, it is necessary to read its meaning, find the main and secondary words in it, read or compose an example (sentence) with this word yourself.

In Russian lessons, when explaining new material, new special terminology is usually introduced (as in other subjects), and new words are introduced as examples illustrating grammatical rules that enrich the speech of students. Also, before the control dictation, the teacher explains words that are incomprehensible to students; when giving a homework assignment from a textbook, he necessarily checks whether everything is clear, whether all the words found in the text are known to students.

Methodological conditions for the formation of the ability to use dictionaries:

- the use of dictionaries in conjunction with the use of a textbook;
- creation of a system of communicative tasks, the solution of which requires access to dictionaries;
- the use of a specially developed system of exercises aimed at mastering the operational components of the ability to use linguistic dictionaries.

Using an explanatory dictionary in Russian language lessons in the process of spelling work will allow you to simultaneously solve various tasks of learning your native language. The materials of explanatory dictionaries, in our opinion, make it possible to compose such exercises that will form the spelling skills of students, as well as enrich their vocabulary, develop thinking and memory. At the same time, it is better if the tasks are given in an entertaining form: in the form of riddles, short sayings, proverbs, poems or puzzles. This will not only enrich their vocabulary, but also develop interest in Russian language lessons. Systematic work with the dictionary will give the necessary skills to work with reference literature, which is necessary, in our opinion, for further training.

The following exercises can be used for students to work with an intelligent dictionary:

1. Searching for the right word in the dictionary. The game "Who is faster?". The teacher asks you to find a word in the explanatory dictionary. The winner is the one who finds the given word faster.

2. Dictionary entry analysis. Selective reading by tasks: - read grammatical marks to the word; - read the lexical meaning of the word; - find in the dictionary entry examples of the interpretation of the meaning of the word.

3. Comparison of two dictionary entries for the same word taken from different dictionaries. Task: to determine which dictionary entry is taken from an explanatory dictionary, and which one is from an encyclopedic one?

4. Compilation of a dictionary entry for encyclopedic and linguistic dictionaries.

5. Creating a dictionary entry based on a plan and drawing. A drawing with an image of an object and a plan are given: The title word - grammatical marks – interpretation of the meaning of the word – examples of usage.

6. Editing the text of the dictionary entry.

Task: 4th grade students decided to make a dictionary of difficult words.

Read one of the dictionary entries. Cross out what seems inappropriate to you. A businessman is a businessman, an entrepreneur who creates values and implements them with his work. A businessman should have a bright head. For example, an enterprising person bought a product in bulk, and then sold this product at a higher price on the market. So he gets a profitable business. That's how he cashes in.

7. Compilation of an explanatory dictionary of the "language of the writer" and (or) individual works (one work).

8. Students are given a task to write out the meanings of words from the proposed list. To complete this task, students resort to the help of an explanatory dictionary;

9. The game "Scrabble". Students need to reveal the meanings of the highlighted words in the proposed list;

10. Dictation "Guess the word!". Students are given interpretations for which they must choose the right words;

11. Lexical dictation. A task that is the exact opposite of the previous one. Students must give an interpretation of the words recorded under dictation;

12. Students are offered a list with words with missing unverifiable letters. Students must find the right words and write them down correctly. Words with similar meanings should be given so that students pay attention to the interpretation of words.

It can be noted that the explanatory dictionary performs the functions of other language dictionaries, such as: orthographic, orthoepic phraseological. And therefore, by teaching children to work with an intelligent dictionary, we also solve important points when studying other sections of the Russian language.

Summing up about working with an intelligent dictionary, I would like to say that, working with this reference manual, children, first of all, learn to operate not only with specific, but also generic concepts. Also, as a result of systematic work with an intelligent dictionary, students develop the ability to quickly and accurately select the necessary words and use them in their own speech and other important skills that simplify the assimilation of new material.

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